

VARIATION IN THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDROGEN CLAY SOLS WITH TEMPERATURE.*

By B. CHATTERJEE AND A. SEN.

In a previous note (Chatterjee and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 646) it has been observed that a hydrogen clay sol H† shows an increase of its free acidity from $0.96 \times 10^{-5}N$ to $2.5 \times 10^{-5}N$ when the temperature is raised from 1° to 50° but gives a constant total acidity ($286 \times 10^{-5}N$) at these temperatures. Results with another hydrogen clay sol Padegaon-B‡ are given in this note (Table I) which show the free acidity, the total acidity and the degree of dissociation all increase with a rise of temperature.

TABLE I.

Colloid content = 3.51 g. per litre.

Free acidity $\times 10^5 N.$			Total acidity $\times 10^5 N.$			Degree of dissociation (%).			p_n at inflexion.		
1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°
1.1	5.0	7.9	200	235	252	0.5	2.1	3.1	9.15	8.15	7.75

The inflexion points become displaced to lower p_n values with increasing temperatures. It is interesting to note that while the total acidity of the hydrogen clay sol H remains constant at different temperatures, that of Padegaon-B increases with increasing temperatures. In view of the differences between the two clays, these temperature variations are being studied further.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY AND COLLOID RESEARCH LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

Received March 17, 1942.

* This work has been carried out under a Scheme of Research into the Properties of Colloid Soil Constituents financed by the Imperial Council of Agricultural Research, India and directed by Prof. J. N. Mukherjee.

† Sols H and Padegaon-B were prepared respectively from the entire clay fractions of a neutral calcareous soil from the Government Seed Farm, Kalyanpore (U. P.) collected from a depth of 0 to 6 inches and a non-lateritic calcareous soil, B-type from Padegaon (Nira, Poona) Farm collected at a depth of 0 to 12 inches.

